

Determination of *pKa* Values of Hydrochlorides of Organic Bases

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The dissociation constants of monosubstituted aniline hydrochlorides determined by conductometric studies in aqueous solutions at 27° are reported in the present paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Monosubstituted anilines were made to react with equimolar quantities of hydrochloric acid in solution. The conductance of aqueous solution of free base and its salt of known strengths was determined by student-type-cambridge-conductometer at 27°. The data collected was treated further in usual way to get *pKa* values. These are reported in Table I.

TABLE I
Average pKa values of hydrochlorides of substituted anilines.

Compound	Formula	<i>pKa</i> values			
		ortho	meta	para	
Aniline-HCl	C ₆ H ₅ -NH ₂ ·HCl	1.8	—	—	—
Toluidine-HCl	CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₅ -NH ₂ ·HCl	—	4.31	4.15	3.72
Chloroaniline-HCl	Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -NH ₂ ·HCl	—	2.58	3.30	3.95
Anisidine-HCl	CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -NH ₂ ·HCl	—	4.52	4.10	5.00
Phenetidine-HCl	C ₂ H ₅ O-C ₆ H ₄ -NH ₂ ·HCl	—	—	—	4.25

The substitution of -methoxy group in para position has the greatest increase in *pKa* value of the amine-hydrochloride, with increased steric effect at the amino group, the effect of *p*-methoxy group is reduced¹. The *pKa* increases with increasing inductive effect of R. It was reported² that *p* and *o*-methyl substitution on benzene ring increases, while *o*- and *p*-chloro-substitution decreases *pKa*. We have obtained the *pKa* values for *o*-toluidine and *o*-chloroaniline-hydrochlorides as 4.31 and 2.58, which are in agreement with Dugar's observations². But in the case of *p*-toluidine and *p*-chloroaniline-hydrochlorides the *pKa* are 3.72 and 3.95.

While studying the surface properties of aqueous solutions of *o*, *m*, and *p*-anisidines Zapior and Czapkiewicz³ have observed the order to be *o* > *m* > *p*, and the *pKa* values to be 9.10, 9.30 and 8.70 in 0.1N KCl at 18°. We have obtained the *pKa* values for the same series to be 4.52, 4.10 and 5.00, in water at 27°. The *m*-anisidine showing the least *pKa*

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value, in agreement with the other properties of many other meta-substituted compounds. Shabarav and coworkers⁴ have reported pK_a values for a series of *o*- and *p*- substituted anilines to study the electron-donating or accepting properties of several substituents. It is known that the trend of inductive effect varies as $Cl > OCH_3 > CH_3$.

In the case of organic bases under study we have $-NH_2$ as one of the substituents in the benzene ring and the relative effect of both the groups in the ring will be responsible for the variation of pK_a of their hydrochlorides. The meta-substituted anilines have pK_a values as *m*-Cl⁻, 3.30; *m*-OCH₃⁻, 4.10; and *m*-CH₃⁻, 4.15. Stewart and O'Donnel⁵ have reported that the effect of ring substitution on the acidity of anilines and diphenylamines are analogous to the ionization of phenols. The pK_a values depend upon temperature and the solvent medium⁶.

In the present cases of a series of mono-substituted aniline hydrochlorides no regular trend in the variation of pK_a values have been observed. Though many theories^{7,8} regarding molecular complexes exist no satisfactory theory has yet been developed to explain the nature of the intramolecular forces existing in such complexes. We may consider here the bond existing between the components to be ionic in nature and attribute the tendency of dissociation to them, which will be responsible for the deviations of the pK_a values.

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